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Digital Twins as a way to help ensure legal compliance of video-based AAL Technologies

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Abstract

The integration of Digital Twins (DTs) in Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) environments offers both opportunities and challenges, particularly in data management, privacy, and ethical considerations. AAL systems aim to enhance the quality of life for older adults through continuous monitoring, but they face significant issues such as data privacy, security, interoperability, and user compliance (Ganesan et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2013).

Data privacy and security are critical in AAL systems, which handle sensitive personal data prone to breaches (Morris et al., 2013). Ensuring secure data storage is challenging due to the diversity of devices. Data quality issues from sensor inaccuracies and the variability in data collection further complicate analysis (Reeder et al., 2013). Interoperability is a significant hurdle as AAL systems often integrate multiple devices, leading to compatibility challenges. Standardization is often lacking, making data aggregation difficult. User compliance is another issue, as elderly users may resist AAL technologies due to privacy concerns or complexity. Efficient data management is crucial but resource-intensive (Pirzada

et al., 2021). Ethical considerations also arise, particularly around autonomy and consent, requiring a balance between the benefits of data collection and individual rights (Manzeschke et al., 2015).

Addressing Challenges with Digital Twin Technology

DTs offer advanced solutions to these challenges. They can enhance data privacy and legal compliance in AAL environments by employing anonymization and pseudonymization techniques (Tao et al., 2019). Edge computing enables localized data processing, reducing the need for data transfer. Federated learning and privacy-preserving analytics, such as differential privacy and homomorphic encryption, allow secure, decentralized processing (Abadi et al., 2016). DTs can simulate environments, using synthetic data for testing and analysis without real-world data, thus improving data protection (Creswell et al., 2018).

DTs improve data quality and reliability by validating data from multiple sources, identifying anomalies before use. Acting as a central hub, DTs address interoperability and standardization issues, integrating data from various devices through standardized protocols (Grieves & Vickers, 2017). They enhance user compliance through personalized feedback and adaptive interfaces that demonstrate the benefits, encouraging adoption. DTs also manage large data volumes efficiently, leveraging cloud and edge processing for real-time analysis, while ethical data collection is ensured by incorporating consent management systems (Pirzada et al., 2021).

DTs adjust to different environments by creating dynamic models, ensuring consistent performance. They simulate scenarios to optimize system performance, improving reliability. Moreover, DTs overcome technological limitations by integrating advancements in sensor technology, ensuring systems are up-to-date and functioning optimally. By testing new technologies virtually, DTs identify potential issues and solutions before implementation, ensuring robust AAL systems.

Despite these advancements, ethical concerns remain, particularly regarding user independence and privacy. The extensive use of AI to monitor behavior could lead to a standardized lifestyle, potentially undermining autonomy (Manzeschke et al., 2015). Privacy concerns also arise from data collection within home environments, potentially leading to the medicalization of private spaces (Mortenson et al., 2015). Ensuring robust, adaptive regulatory frameworks is crucial to addressing these challenges, particularly in enhancing privacy protection and legal compliance.

Technical and Legal Framework

This research integrates technical analysis and doctrinal legal research to address these challenges. The technical analysis examines DTs' architecture and functionalities in AAL, assessing compliance with legal requirements. Collaboration with academic professionals provides practical insights, enhancing the study. Doctrinal research meticulously examines the GDPR, MDR, and AI Act, interpreting legislative texts to ensure compliance. The study also reviews existing societal implications of DTs in AAL. Ethical considerations, privacy concerns, and the potential social impact of deploying DTs are explored, focusing on balancing the benefits of these technologies with the need to protect individual rights. This comprehensive approach ensures well-rounded findings and recommendations for stakeholders involved in AAL technologies' development and regulation.

Conclusions

Proportionality and compromising represent two distinct dimensions of balancing, embodying disparate approaches, and functioning as disparate metaphors. However, they do not appear to be mutually exclusive. Rather, they may complement each other.

Proposing a method of balancing that reconciles proportionality and compromising would be a significant theoretical contribution with practical implications. Hence, it should be a subject of further research.

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